

A Critical Study on Drug Abuse among Youths

Dr. Lora Aptaprava

Abstract:

Today, it has become a worldwide disorder, equally affecting the economically depressed, middle class, upper class and ultra-modern social groups. A large number of youth community and students in Indian cities are affected by this drug addiction. Farmers and laborers in rural areas are also plagued by this drug addiction. Many studies on drug-addiction expose that the problem of drug abuse and alcoholism is not limited to urban areas only, but also continues in rural areas.

The True Care Trust a social welfare organization continues to make an undeniable contribution in the rehabilitation of drug addicts. Special treatment centers, rehabilitation centers have been set up in urban as well as rural areas all over India by social welfare organizations to free the alcoholic and drug addicts from this disorder. National Drug Dependence Treatment Center in Delhi, Lal Bahadur Shastri Hospital, in Mumbai. For this, every citizen of the country needs to have a sense of awareness and strict steps need to be taken to rid the country of addiction.

Introduction:

Drug addiction has become a major cause of concern throughout the world. It is a destructive state that has been in turmoil for a decade and must end. Drug addiction is synonymous with substance abuse disorder. Plight of victims of such torture. It affects them mentally, physically and emotionally. In India, substance abuse disorders include narcotics, sedatives and stimulants. Opium and heroin are similar examples. A drug addict loses control over his mind and indulges in activities considered illegal to mankind- kidnapping, murder, robbery, theft and the list is endless. It also harms their relationships because this type of addiction can have an adverse effect on their mood - they can sometimes become very aggressive and even murderous. We need to

help such people. It is not easy to get rid of addiction all at once. It is a long and gradual process and must be dealt with wisely and intelligently. Due to the consumption of drugs, people forget their normal activities and become dependent on others.¹ And if the youth of the country get addicted to drugs and becomes dependent then destruction becomes inevitable. People become drug addicts when their interest in drugs increases. Drug addiction is when someone cannot stop using drugs, even if they want to and even if it harms them. It is like a strong pull that compels them to take the substance.² Over time, the person may need more of the drug to get the same feeling. If they try to quit, they may feel very sick or in a bad mood. This happens because their body gets used to the drug. Addiction is not just about willpower; It is a medical condition in which the brain changes and makes it difficult to let go. It is important for people with addictions to get help because it can seriously affect their health and lives. Drug consumption causes different reactions in the brain and body of each person. A person does not immediately become addicted to a drug, but long-term use of the drug significantly increases a person's risk of becoming addicted to it.

Families are often profoundly affected, experiencing emotional distress, financial strain, and relationship problems. Substance abuse can disrupt family dynamics, leading to neglect, domestic violence, and instability within the household. Children growing up in such environments are at higher risk of developing their own substance use disorders or experiencing other adverse outcomes.³ On a broader scale, drug

¹ Criminology & Penology by Prof. N.V. Paranjape, Eighteenth Edition 2019, Central Law Publications.

² Drug Addiction, A Psycho-social Study of Youth, Dr. J. C. Parikh & K. S. Krishna, Friends Publications (India)

³ Criminology by Ram Ahuja, Rawat Publications.

addiction has significant societal implications. It contributes to increased healthcare costs, strain on the criminal justice system, and loss of productivity in the workforce. MAT has shown significant effectiveness in reducing opioid overdose deaths and improving treatment outcomes. These groups offer a platform for individuals to share their experiences, gain support from others who have faced similar challenges, and find motivation to maintain abstinence. In recent years, harm reduction approaches have gained recognition as valuable strategies to mitigate the adverse consequences of drug addiction.⁴

Review of Literature:

R.M Karla (2005) said, Nations can rise from the ashes of physical destruction, but there is no hope for nations, where the young generation has been psychologically destroyed”, the above statement clearly indicates the importance of the youngsters in building a mighty nation. So as a nurse, the investigator felt the need to take up the responsibility in building a strong nation by educating the youths and thus prevent substance abuse among college students who are the pillars of our developing nation.

Wallace et al., (2003) conducted a pre-experimental study on substance abuse and ill effect on adolescents and study reveals that it is important also to keep inter-racial variations in drug and alcohol use in mind when comparing the prevalence of substance use with that of other races. For instance, the findings from the 1985-1989 Monitoring the Future surveys that show that American Indian and white male binge drinking rates were identical would seem encouraging until one considers that both groups were twice as likely as African. American males and 2.5 times more likely than Asian-American males to have consumed 5 or more drinks in one setting in the 2 weeks prior to the survey. In other words, it isn't necessarily a good thing that American Indian adolescents' drug and alcohol use patterns approach those of white adolescents because those white adolescents also

have substance use “issues” when considered in light of the experiences of minorities.

Chatterjee, (2019) However, there is some proof that reception of medication-assisted treatments influences treatment duration among youths. Researchers examining a sample of more than 4,500 youths ages 13 to 22 found that youths who received opioid use disorder medication (e.g., buprenorphine, naltrexone) within 3 months of diagnosis with an opioid use disorder stayed in treatment longer than those who did not receive the medication (150 days of treatment, compared with 67 days of treatment).

Drake, (2012) The author examines youth substance use treatment programs aim to reduce alcohol and illicit drug use, and the misuse of licit drugs, in youths who have been clinically diagnosed with a substance use problem. These programs differ from prevention programs, which aim to promote abstinence in youths to prevent their initial or escalating use. Treatment programs can take a multitude of approaches, such as court-based, residential-based, and family-inclusive programs to help youth develop skills and knowledge to reduce substance use.

Issues and Challenges:

Emerging issues and challenges within the area of drug dependency hold to form the landscape of substance abuse and its remedy.

Artificial Drugs and Dressmaker Drugs

The distribution of artificial pills, which include artificial cannabinoids, cathinone's (bath salts), and synthetic opioids, pose challenges to drug enforcement and public fitness efforts. Those materials frequently have unpredictable outcomes and may be stronger and perilous than conventional pills.

Stigma and Limitations To Treatment

Stigma related to drug addiction remains a vast barrier to in search of help and having access to treatment. Efforts to lessen stigma, enhance public training, and promote compassionate and non-judgmental techniques to addiction are essential for encouraging individuals to trying to find help.

Global Drug Alternate and Prepared Crime

⁴ Criminology, Penology & Victimology by Dr. S. S. Srivastava, Central Law Agency, 2021.

Organized criminal networks make the most vulnerabilities in supply chains, stay away from law enforcement, and gas violence and instability in affected regions. Addressing these emerging developments and demanding situations calls for a comprehensive and coordinated response involving governments, healthcare specialists, regulation enforcement organizations, community companies, and people affected by drug dependency. It necessitates a shift towards proof-based totally tactics, damage reduction techniques, improved get right of entry to treatment and aid offerings, and a focus on addressing the underlying factors contributing to substance abuse. Collaboration and innovation are vital to effectively cope with the evolving nature of drug dependency and its effect on people and communities.

Epidemic:

The wide spread epidemic remains a substantial task globally, with the misuse and abuse of prescription opioids, in addition to the upward push in illicit opioids like heroin and fentanyl, leading to a surge in overdoses and fatalities. Addressing this crisis requires a multifaceted technique, which includes advanced get entry to proof-based remedy, extended damage discount services, and better regulation of prescription opioids.

Poly Drug Use and Novel Substances

People might also combine exceptional pills or mix substances with alcohol, growing the chance of damaging results and overdose. The emergence of novel psychoactive substances, regularly bought as "felony highs" or "research chemicals," offers challenges in terms of law, monitoring, and supplying accurate records to the public approximately their dangers.

Technological Advances

The technology advances have each fine and negative implications for drug addiction. On one hand, it enables get entry to statistics, on-line help organizations, and health offerings for remote treatment and counselling. However, the internet and social media systems additionally permit the advertising and sale of illicit substances, making it hard to adjust and combat online drug markets.

Role of Judiciary

The Indian government has taken various steps to make India drug free. Various laws have been

formulated so that crime does not occur in the society due to this addiction. The Judiciary Department felt that there is a need to keep an eye on all the things coming from these countries where the drug trade is going on, the police and the army should act with great awareness and fearlessness, and it is the duty of all people to over surveillance because for the welfare of the society it is very necessary to stop this smuggling, because if it is not monitored then the society will one day go towards destruction, it is known that according to 2012 and 2013 report India is involved in the drug net market as a result of 2022 and according to the report more than 60000 Cases involving more drugs are allocated to trial courts. A large number of cases are being registered daily in the Indian justice system due to this drug power, so the Indian justice system is very active in the form of drug power. A drug addict has done something against his will in which his family and himself are facing danger all over the country. The global situation is becoming dangerous almost every day, according to Indian law if no person forces another person. By forcing another person to perform any act, both the person who performs the act and the person who compels him to do the act shall be guilty of the same offence.

The work of the judiciary is how important the law that the legal system makes is in the society and as a result, how well the people of the society are doing and whether the law and order is being properly implemented, whether the people are protecting this law and order and whether they are breaking the law, if a person breaks the law and order, then stricter and stricter against him. administer punishment. Judiciary chiefs have been discussing the use of sociological methods in addition to punitive measures to prevent these drug traffickers and drug users from becoming first-class people in society.

The Judiciary took an important initiative that the Narcos Coordination Center should provide financial support to the States to control the addiction, and the Center would order the States to properly review and consider a person addicted to the drug. Through its NDPs law, the judicial system has been amended by Parliament to make some changes in the NDPSE law, (1998, 2021, 2024) to strictly monitor the production, sale and manufacture of narcotics etc.

Numerous prison acts were passed to modify and manage the manufacture, sale, distribution, and possession of medicine and poisons. The WHO (1996) defines a drug as any substance or product that is used or supposed for use to regulate or explore physiological structures or pathological states for the advantage of the recipient. As per the Drug and Beauty Act, the drug includes all medicines for the inner or external use of people or animals and all materials meant to be used for or within the analysis, remedy, mitigation,⁵ or prevention of any ailment or ailment in humans or animals such as coaching applied on the human frame to repel bugs like mosquitoes. Poison is defined as any substance which while delivered into the residing body or introduced into contact with any part thereof will produce ill effect or death utilizing its local or systemic motion.

Conclusion:

Drug addiction and crime today has become an obstacle in the progress of the social system, to be honest, to keep these obstacles moving forward and active these days our leaders, ministers and governance departments and administrative departments have given some importance, because we have not done any work with an intoxicated person. It is very easy, moreover, keeping in mind that it is possible to earn a huge amount of money from all these addictions, it will not be wrong to say that the established and respected people in the society are involved in these.

This study's evaluation's reason is to help the reader recognize exclusive elements posed by using the research on the Deaf community's rejection of cochlear implants. that is sizable due to the fact many listening human beings have a different method for cochlear implants than the Deaf do, frequently not knowing there are different points of view. there were a great deal of studies and discussions performed on those opinions of the Deaf community, inclusive of culture, eugenics resulting in cultural genocide, and conflicts with a loss of identity. maximum of the

⁵ Drug Addiction, A Psycho-social Study of Youth, Dr. J. C. Parikh & K. S. Krishna, Friends Publications (India).

research determined changed into at the Deaf subculture and its components. Greater studies and trying out are required to gain a higher knowledge of why people who undergo cochlear implants are facing the confusion and conflict of no longer figuring out with both institutions. it's far crucial to conduct more studies at the results and reasons they sense neglected of a group and feature low.

Suggestions:

1. Behavioral therapies, motivational interviewing, and contingency management, are commonly used in addiction treatment. These therapies help individuals identify and develop coping skills, and maintain abstinence.
2. Successful rehabilitation often involves aftercare support and ongoing treatment to maintain long-term recovery. Acceptance of personal responsibility and a willingness to seek help are crucial.
3. Prevention efforts also can contain implementing stricter policies at the pharmaceutical industry to lessen the provision and over-prescription of addictive materials.
4. Moreover, investing in research and improvement for alternative ache control strategies and non-addictive medicinal drugs can help alleviate the reliance on opioids and other pills.
5. This collaborative method can assist in figuring out and addressing the basis reasons of addiction, inclusive of mental fitness troubles or social determinants of fitness.
6. Emphasis on the importance of prevention in reducing drug abuse quotes is every other key factor of this holistic approach. by means of focusing on prevention strategies, which includes schooling and attention programs.

References:

1. Criminology & Penology by Prof. N.V. Paranjape, Eighteenth Edition 2019, Central Law Publications.
2. Drug Addiction, A Psycho-social Study of Youth, Dr. J. C. Parikh & K. S. Krishna, Friends Publications (India).
3. Criminology, Penology & Victimology by Dr. S. S. Srivastava, Central Law Agency, 2021.

4. Textbook on Criminology, composed by Katherine S. Williams, Oxford University Press, 7th edition.
5. Criminology by Ram Ahuja, Rawat Publications.
6. Criminology & Penology by Prof. N.V. Paranjape, Eighteenth Edition 2019, Central Law Publications.
7. Narcotic Drugs, Anil Aggarwal, National Book Trust, India.
8. Drug Addiction, A Psycho-social Study of Youth,
9. Dr. J. C. Parikh & K. S. Krishna, Friends Publications (India).